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The attempt is made to initially arrange in the terms of methodology the area of the research on partner roles in homoerotic relations. These issues have been noticed very early in human history, e.g., different roles performed or bimodal polarization, but only recently the science become interested in this. It is suggested to cover all such roles by the term sexual partner roles (SPR) instead of various terms used and to classify them according to the ethological evolutionary approach into the appetitive and consummatory SPR. Further details of the division are discussed, and the utility of such classification is marked.

KEYWORDS homosexuality, sexual partner roles, sex role preference, classification, ethological evolutionary approach

A HISTORY OF THE ISSUE

The issue of the roles of sexual partners in the same-sex relationships is rarely undertaken in the scientific literature, although it is of great importance for understanding human sexuality and it deserves more attention. However, several publications discussing the topic have already been published, and it seems that there is a need to attempt to initially arrange this field of research in the methodological context.

It should be noted that although only recently have the scholars started to discuss this issue, it must have certainly been noticed much earlier by humans in general. The awareness of the existence of different partner roles in homosexual behavior was certainly present from the moment that this type of behavior appeared among men. From some of the laws recorded in a Middle Assyrian code from the 2nd millennium BC, we can learn for example, that a man who actively acted in such encounters was not condemned, but it was the passive partner who was

treated by the community with contempt because his action was seen not natural, and his ‘feminine’ approach excluded him from among the males (see, e.g., Nissinen, 1998). The awareness of the existence of different sexual roles is also clearly visible in the Assyrian divination manual *Summa alu*, where it was is inter alia stated that: *If a man has sex per anion with his social peer, that man will become foremost among his brothers and colleagues* (Nissinen, 2010, p. 75). Interestingly, similar attitudes towards homosexuality have survived until the present day. In some countries, the active partner is very often not considered a homosexual but only the passive one is (see Faubion, 1993; Prieur, 1996; Carrier, 1985; Alonso, Koreck, 1988; Phellas, 2005; Carrara, Simões, 2008; for more references see Jeffries IV, 2009). A similar approach is common in prison subcultures (see, e.g., Hensley, 2001; Gagnon, Simon, 2005) or among American adolescent boys (Pascoe, 2005). In many traditional cultures, homosexual behavior has also been differentiated in various ways due to the roles that the sexual partners played. The most prominent example of this, known in the literature and repeatedly cited, is the male initiation rites of some tribes, in which young people make a ritual *fellatio* for older natives or they are penetrated *per anum* (cf., Carrier, 1977; Herdt, 1981; 1984; Kimmel, 2006; Kowalski, 2011).

In ancient Athens, various names was used to describe the roles in homosexual intercourses, most often the passive partner was called *pais*, a boy, or *erōmenes*, a beloved, while the active partner was called *paidika*, of boys, or *erastēs*, a lover (Dover, 2004). In the book *Problems* attributed to Aristotle, and at least coming from his school, the reasons were considered why some men take pleasure from a homosexual act (Aristotle, 1970, IV, 26). It is supposed that this may be the result of abnormal body composition of some men that makes them slightly alike to the female body and make the men experiencing pleasure not through a genital stimulation, but rather by an anal one. The issue considered by Pseudo-Aristotle is an important question that the science still cannot finally answer (as to the hypothesis on a role the prostate plays in this phenomenon see Morin, 1998; Hoppe, 2011). While in the case of

heterosexual behavior, the roles of women and men are clearly defined by the biological conditions of both partners, in the case of homosexual relations, on both sides, we deal with individuals of essentially the same anatomical features, what raises a question about what the causes make that in each homosexual act the first person adopts one role, and the second person adopts the other, and in addition these roles complement each other. In some cases, of course, it might be a matter of a fully free, unlimited agreement between the partners who are determined for sexual contact with the same-sex person in any way, but in many cases, a person has a more or less clearly defined range of preferences as possible for his sexual role, and the formation process of such, but no other, predispositions of these persons requires an explanation. It should be noted that this is not so much a question about the causes of homosexuality as such, but rather a question of psychophysiological mechanisms that govern its internal diversity, although it is possible that these two issues are related to each other more closely than it was previously thought.

Michel Foucault captured the question of roles of sexual partners as an important and clearly separate component of any sexual relations. In his view, the diversity of the roles has been noticed much earlier than the separateness of the phenomenon of homosexuality itself. 'Role' or 'polarity specific', as he defines it, in the sexual behavior, has already been distinguished in the ancient times (Foucault, 1984/1985). He writes about the ancient Greek verb *aphrodisiazein* (to copulate):

but the verb can also be employed in its active sense, in which case it relates specifically to the so-called 'masculine' role in intercourse, and to the active function defined by penetration. And inversely, one can use it in its passive form – aphrodisiasthēnai – designating in this case the other role in sexual union: the 'passive' role of the object partner. This role is the one that nature had set aside for women; (...) it is the role that could be imposed by force on someone who was thus reduced to being the object of the other's pleasure; it is also the role accepted by the boy or man who let himself be penetrated by his partner (ibid., p. 46).

However, the problematization of homosexuality as a separate phenomenon has become a fact, according to Foucault, only from the moment of the scientific sexology appearance, the event that was even dated accurately by the scholar as the year 1870 (Foucault, 1976/1978, p. 43). Discussing the nineteenth-century stereotypical image of a homosexual, he indicates two different phenomena:

in the deeply negative intensity of this stereotype, one might read the age-old difficulty, for our societies, of integrating these two phenomena – different phenomena at that – of the inversion of sexual roles and intercourse between individuals of the same sex (Foucault, 1984/1985, p. 18).

A similar problem in sociological terms is discussed by Bourdieu (1998/2001). According to him, the dichotomous active-passive symbolism is very important to understand both the concept of gender and the foundation of male domination. This symbolism is so deeply embedded in patterns of social perception and value systems that the existence of such a dichotomy may be seen as something completely natural and obvious.

For a long time, sexology did not pay enough attention to this issue. In the second half of the 19th century, homosexuality was understood mostly as role reversal, so-called sexual inversion (see, e.g., Bem, 1993; Greenberg, 1988). Although, as mentioned by Wilson (2001, p. 191), in 1889 French journalist Ali Coffignon published the book in which he made an amateur classification of homosexuals. First, he divided them into two categories: the active and the passive, and within these two groups, he distinguished three further subgroups. The psychoanalysis, in its various sections and branches, devoted much attention to the homosexual inclinations, but initially, including Freud, it failed to perceive the issue of sexual partner roles and it often confused this and mixed the homosexuality as such with mental femininity-masculinity (Friedman, 1986, pp. 74-75).

Brown (1957; 1958) was one of the first scholars who noticed the necessity to differentiate between the sex-role inversion and homosexuality. While the term 'inversion' refers to the adoption of a sex role and the introjection of the psychological identity of the opposite sex, the concept of homosexuality refers to sexual desire and activity between two members of the same sex. Brown stated (p. 613):

while certain forms of homosexuality (passive male and active female) are expressions of personality inversion, other forms of homosexuality have nothing to do with inversion. Failure to observe this basic distinction results in confusion, both in theory and research.

At the same time, Grygier (1957) suggested that scores on the femininity-masculinity scales in personality tests vary due to the active or passive role in homosexual activity. Bieber *et al.* (1962) attempted to establish a neutral, scientific terminology instead of the previously used colloquial and ambiguous names. They coined the neologism 'insertor' to denote a person who is active in an anal intercourse and passive at a *fellatio*, while the 'insertee' means the passive partner in an anal intercourse and the receptive one in oral sex. Hooker (1965) essentially upheld the distinction proposed by Brown and the terminology proposed by Bieber *et al.* She wrote about the *passive male homosexual, or invert* and the *active, or masculine homosexual* (p. 25). She also observed the terms that were being used by a City Health personnel attending the study: the 'dominant' and the 'receptive roles' as equivalent terms for the insertor and insertee (p. 34). However, Haist & Hewitt (1974) pointed that the majority of homosexuals do not conform to the commonly used labels.

The study on the need to distinguish between sex roles and sex orientation was undertaken by Ross (1975). He also empirically investigated the accuracy of the assumption that male homosexual are either active or passive in sexual practices, and he found that about half of the studied group exhibited equal preference for both, and many of them preferred oral and other mutual activities. Also, Harry (1977) arrived at similar conclusions.

Carrier (1977) introduced the term 'sex-role preference' and pointed that it is an important explanatory variable. He followed Hooker (1962) in making distinction between 'sex role' and 'gender role'. The first refers to typical sexual performance only, without assuming the gender connotations (masculinity-femininity) in these performances, while the second refers to "expected attitudes and behaviors that distinguish males from females". Carrier provided the names for the roles that partners may play in sexual encounters: active or passive, dominant or submissive, insertor or insertee, as well as the types of sexual practices: the mutual manipulation of genitals, general body friction, and friction within anal or oral orifice.

In the second half of the 1980s, students started to be interested in sexual roles in the same-sex intercourses in the context of the risk of HIV infection. It was quickly noticed that the image of homoerotic behaviors as bipolar is oversimplified. In fact, most often only the intercourses are bipolar, while the underlying predispositions of a substantial part of partners in this regard present a considerable degree of flexibility. Wiley, Herschkorn (1989) investigated the effect of differentiation of roles in homosexual intercourses on the size of AIDS epidemic, taking into account various sex-role subgroups, and they proved that "epidemic intensity increases with increasing size of the dual-role (both insertive and receptive) subpopulation". Weinrich et al. (1992) adopted the previously proposed terms insertor and insertee, and they named the roles performed in sexual intercourses as 'genitoerotic roles'. They also distinguished the preferences for insertive or receptive approach in anal intercourses from the similar preferences in oral-genital and oral-anal contacts. Coxton et al. (1993) investigated the prevalence of types of sex roles in behaviors among gay men and found a certain degree of roles rigidity, but this rigidity is not large enough to conclude that gay men exclusively engage in either an active or a passive role. Van Druten *et al.* (1996) use the term 'homosexual behavior roles' in the context of the risk of spread of HIV infection. They distinguished between 'receptive' and 'insertive anal intercourse' and found that changes in the roles of behavior distributions influence the spread of HIV.

Wegesin & Meyer-Bahlburg (2000) drew attention to the phenomenon of self-labeling occurring in the gay community that involves naming the partners by some hackneyed, colloquial phrases according to the role played by them in sexual relations. Under this nomenclature, an inserter is called the 'top' and an insertee is called the 'bottom'. These authors have also studied what is the interplay between the way of performing the roles that were declared using these labels and real behavior, and they found that there is a high degree of compatibility between them. Hart *et al.* (2003) studied the phenomenon of self-labeling, too, and found that 88% of people were using the labels 'top', 'bottom' and 'versatile' and that there was a high degree of consistency between labeled and real sexual roles. Researchers have developed an interesting original scale of preferences for receptive or insertive intercourses, in which the subjects separately assess their predispositions for anal and oral sex on 5-point Linkert-type scales. Carballo-Diéguez *et al.* (2004) found that adoption of the insertive or receptive roles partly depends on partners' characteristic. Ridge (2004) argued that the roles are organized around the partners' meanings of masculinity. Moskowitz *et al.* (2008) established that self-labels regarding partners' roles, i.e., the top, bottom, and versatile, were correlated with corresponding roles within sexual behavior, aside from intercourses. In a study based on a large sample, Jeffries IV (2009) analyzed the differences in preferences for receptive or insertive sex roles between Latino and non-Latino gay men, whereas in another large survey Grov *et al.* (2010) investigated differences in gay men's sexual positioning with their partners depending on their penis size. Moskowitz and Hart (2011) conducted a survey on a sample of 429 gay men, in which they found the existence of objective, and not only subjective, premises that determine the intra-individual preferences towards the role in homosexual relations. Wei & Raymond (2011) highlighted that sex roles are an important aspect of identities and cultures among gay men, and they explored sociodemographic and behavioral correlates of preferences for such roles. Lately, Johns *et al.* (2012) studied the influence of gender roles and interpersonal factors on positioning in homosexual acts. Similarly, Zheng *et al.* (2012) found meaningful

differences between homosexual self-label groups in gendered traits and interest. Most recently, can be seen a tendency to use again the ambiguous term ‘sex role’ or an periphrasis such as ‘role during sexual intercourse’ (e.g., Armbruster *et al.*, 2013; Doerner *et al.*, 2013; Valentova *et al.*, 2014).

The discussed issue has also gained a significant attention of social constructionists. In part, they follow the distinctions and senses that Michel Foucault, their well-known precursor, pointed, and that were mentioned here yet. The dichotomy of ‘active’ and ‘passive’ male homosexuals received more recent interpretation of sex behavior *entirely in terms of rigid ideas of ‘masculinity’ and ‘femininity’, and it also reinforced the distinction between ‘true’ (feminine) and ‘pseudo’ (masculine) homosexuality* (Plummer, 1981, p. 147). However, there is another else, vast current of the research pertaining the dynamics of interpersonal relations in intimate couples. These relations are recognized as a result of *the negotiation of day-to-day life in couples or in the community* (ibidem, p. 124). How it is pointed, in such relations, there are still reflected the internalized, general societal values and beliefs that could be called ‘heteropatriarchal’, and this lead to the inequality of the partners and sexual abuses (Cruz, 2000; Hearn, 2004). At a ground of these disturbed relations is laid a stereotypical, asymmetrical perception of the two parts where the one is perceived as ‘hyper-masculine’, or ‘masculine-acting’, and the second, viewed as ‘feminine’, or ‘feminine-acting’, is often ‘othering’. So the dominant partners seek to mirror the traditional heterosexual gender orders with men’s hegemony and try to subordinate the feminine-acting counterparts (Connell & Messerschmidt, 2005; Hearn, 2004). Moreover, the ‘feminine’ part is sometimes, in extreme instances, recognized as “sissy”, what may impose a “sissyphobia” (see, e.g., Eguchi, 2011). Two interesting studies addressed specifically the issue of the gay partners’ roles in sex within this perspective. Kippax & Smith (2001) consider the roles as a relation of power between men where power is thought as a domination or negotiable dynamics. In turn, Hoppe (2011) termed

the role performing as the ‘positional identity’, and he argued that the identities are construed in the frame of culturally structurized sexual scripts.

The issue of women's sexual roles in homoerotic relations is probably even less investigated than those regarding men. Singh *et al.* (1999) studied psychobiological correlates of ‘butch’ and ‘femme’ erotic roles, and they found the validity of such classification. Brown *et al.* (2002) explored possible biological differences between ‘butch’ and ‘femme’ lesbians. Rosario *et al.* (2007) examined whether any considerable differences exist in the sexual identity formation and integration between the butch and femme women. Zheng & Zheng (2011) noted that lesbians use the same sexual self-labels as gay men but with some different sense of those terms. Among Chinese lesbians the following labels are common: the ‘T’ for those who prefer the active role during sexual intercourse, the ‘P’ for those who prefer the receptive role, and the ‘H’ for the ones enjoying both roles equally. In a survey by Walker *et al.* (2012), in turn, the scholars explored the intersection between lesbian gender labels, i.e., butch, soft butch, butch/femme, and femme, and attraction to sexual behaviors, and they did not confirm that the sexual behavior of the participants significantly differs according to the labels.

The phenomenon of self-labeling refers primarily to the phrases that are commonly used within the gay community. As it has been shown by the studies cited, the labels do not always have to be understood in the same way by all gay people, especially those with a rather loose contact with the community or with no such contact at all. However, the manner in which the communities define the roles of partners in sex may be interesting for students of sexual behavior and meaningful, e.g., when formulating questions in a questionnaire survey. To look more closely at this issue, for the paper’s purposes, there have been performed an overview of some of the most popular and most trafficked Internet sites for gay people seeking partners, the so called ‘dating websites’. The data from such five different dating sites has been taken into account, i.e., those sites which, according to Wikipedia, are amid the largest undertakings of this type: 1) adam4adam.com¹, 2) manhunt.net², 3) gay.com³, 4) gayromeo.com/

planetromeo.com⁴, 5) gaydar.co.uk⁵. Such portals require users to register and provide a certain amount of information characterizing the person, i.e., the creation of the so-called profile, which content is available to other users. Among the data collected, there is also a request to enter the preferred role that the user would like to play in sexual relations. Table 1 contains a list of phrases, which are used in this context on those websites. A strong need to use such labels in the all observed gay community sites proves that the categorization has got significant practical usefulness.

Table 1. The terms of roles of sexual partners by the selected dating websites for gays

www	adam4adam.com	gaydar.co.uk	gayromeo.com	manhunt.net	gay.com
terms of roles	bottom	passive	bottom only	bottom	receiver/bottom
	versatile/bottom	passive/versatile	more bottom	bottom/versatile	-
	versatile	versatile	versatile	versatile	switch/versatile
	versatile/top	active/versatile	more top	top/versatile	-
	top	active	top only	top	giver/top

Last access to the all sites: 22.10.2013.

AN ATTEMPT OF CLASSIFICATION

The variety of terminology and the number of ways the issue is discussed makes it very difficult to advance research in this area, including the comparisons of the results of research, and the use of the earlier findings. It seems justified, therefore, to try to bring a preliminary methodological order to these issues. One of the first step, as stipulated by the methodology of science, is to make a typology or classification of these phenomena or facts on which our judgments are formulated, wherein the typology is considered to be a form of less comprehensive, complete and unambiguous classification (Bailey, 1994).

Classifications are performed relatively rare in the field of sex research that does not concern clinical aspects, probably due to the extremely complex nature of sexual behaviors, difficult to elaborate strict definitions. One of the more significant attempts was the taxonomy, which, in the context of gender-oriented sexual behavior, was offered by Devor (1993). In the field of the research on homosexuality, a typology of male bar patrons was proposed in terms of their degree of self-disclosure of sexual orientation (Myrick, 1974), a typology of non-heterosexual male collegiate identities (Dilley, 2005), or a typology of effeminacies in a broader cultural context (Hennen, 2011).

First of all, we should distinguish between the issue of the roles of partners in the sexual act and much broader issue of the individual's sex role in the society, known in the literature as sex roles (social sex roles), or gender roles (cf., e.g., Bem, 1975; 1995; Hochschild, 1973). These roles are performed by individuals even if they have no current sexual partner, and largely are publicly performed while the roles of sexual partner are played mostly in isolation, and then have the interpersonal, dyadic character. The role of discourse on gender in the disentanglement of the discourse on homosexuality was discussed, e.g., by Oudshoorn (1995); Rosenzweig, Lebow (1992); Bailey *et al.* (1997); Levitt, Hiestand (2005) or Sandfort (2005).

Since the tradition of using the term 'sex roles' in a social context had already been firmly established in the science, it was necessary to adopt another, distinctive name for these roles in the strictly sexual context. Many different phrases have appeared, and the list based on the reviewed literature is presented in Table 2. How it is seen, it is difficult to find even two identical names to specify the same phenomenon. From the analysis of the list, it is possible to deduce that all the terms are related to the roles that sexual partners mutually play, so it seems that they could be covered in one inclusive, general name: *sexual partner roles* (SPR). In the case of conventional and colloquial expressions, linguistic misunderstandings can easily occur in relation to non-anal intercourse, because the terms 'active' and 'passive' usually have the opposite meaning than in the case of an anal intercourse. The term 'insertor' has the advantage over the remaining types of terms because in both cases it suggests the person who is experiencing sexual gratification thanks to his genitals.

----- [The suggested place for Table 2] -----

When attempting to classify, we are starting with a distinction which is often made in the literature between different variations of sexual acts, such as genito-genital, oral-genital, oral-anal, masturbatory, etc. In each of these types of behavior, each role listed in Table 1 can

virtually occur. As it seems, different types of homosexual acts not only have different behavioral characteristics but also unequal importance from the other points of view, for example, from the ethological and evolutionary viewpoint. It is known that not all sexual behaviors originate in a straight line from our evolutionary ancestors, and not all find their evolutionary counterparts in other organisms (e.g., mammals); some of these behaviors are specific and unique to humans (see, e.g., Bagemihl, 1999). From this point of view, it is possible to make quite clear arrangement of homosexual acts with those that are an approximate equivalent, an analogue of the classical heterosexual genito-genital acts, appropriate for most organisms reproducing by sex, and with all those that may not be included there. The former should include anogenito-anogenital homosexual acts, while the others cover oral-genital, oral-anal acts, masturbatory techniques, and others.

Subsequently, it is worth noticing that all the sexual behaviors that we have previously taken into account refer to such actions that provide sexual gratification for at least one of the partners, and can thus be defined as consummatory behavior. In regard to the behavior based on instinctual ground, the distinction between the consummatory phase and the preceding appetite phase has yet a long tradition in ethology (see, e.g., Manning, 1972), and is also being widely accepted in psychology (see, e.g., Kappas, 2011). Hence, it seems reasonable to identify all the SPR discussed so far as the *consummatory sexual partner roles* and to presume that it is possible to indicate such roles of sexual partners that are performed in the appetite phase of sexual behavior. It seems that the homoerotic *appetence sexual partner roles* also deserve the researchers' attention, i.e., their attempts to describe and understand them. For example, the possible parallels between similar roles in homosexual and heterosexual relationships may prove interesting. One can expect that quite different relationships exist between consummatory and appetite SPR in both types of sexual behaviors. It seems that a person in the passive homosexual act does not need to show passivity in the phase of courtship, seduction and foreplay.

Finally, therefore, the proposed classification of SPR is exposed in following way:

1. appetitive SPR
2. consummatory SPR
 - 2.1. anogenito-anogenital SPR
 - 2.2. non-anogenito-anogenital SPR
 - 2.2.1. anogenito-oral SPR
 - 2.2.1.1. genito-oral SPR
 - 2.2.1.2. ano-oral SPR
 - 2.2.2. the others (partner masturbatory, etc.).

In supplementation to the classification there could be developed an auxiliary typology of the SPR's. In studies that are included in our review, a certain degree of variability has been shown, i.e., flexibility in choosing the roles possible to perform. Such flexibility may be present at any given time (in regard to sexual orientation see, e.g., LeVay, 1996; McConaghy, 1999; Epstein *et al.*, 2012), but it can also evolve over a person's lifetime (in regard to sexual orientation see, e.g., Baumeister, 2000; Kinnish *et al.*, 2005; Subhi *et al.*, 2011). The concept of the role fluidity in relation to a given person raises a question of consistency between the role which is the object of the person's desires, plans, imaginations and the role that is performed in the reality. All manifestations of SPR may be therefore analyzed on two levels:

- intentional SPR (desires, plans, imaginations, etc.)
- behavioral SPR (real conducts).

LeVay (1996) discussed some essential classification problems in sexual research and he proposed the two another else levels of classification in regard to people's sexual orientation, specifically the criterion of the physiological response for erotic stimuli and the criterion of subject's self-identification with a sexual orientation. For the research of SPR, the psychophysiological methods of measure (LeVay, 1996; McConaghy, 1999) seem to have a

little, if any, usefulness. As to self-identification, it is the question of a choice (or a need) whether to treat this one as the part of the intentional states of the person or as a separate level of analysis. A schematic and rough character of typology allows each way.

Each of the roles may obviously occur on each of the levels. Additionally, one can examine the occurrence of various roles at both levels in the past, the present and the future. In this regard, we follow similar assumptions as the authors of the Klein Grid (Klein *et al.*, 1985) adopted in respect to the assessment of sexual orientation.

An overwhelming majority of the studies that have been already discussed concerns male homosexuality, also the proposed classification in the first place applies to this phenomenon. It is a matter of the further research determining to what extent the roles adopted in female homosexual behaviors are possible to arrange in the same way, and to what extent in completely different than those included in the presented classification.

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed classification might prove to be cognitively useful. The distinctions between the different sub-groups within the population of homosexuals, which are facilitated by the classification, should be taken into account wherever possible in the course of surveys and when formulating theories. In each of these instances, one should indicate a population or its part to which his findings shall be applied. As it was aptly observed yet in 1957 by Trevor C.N. Gibbens, the reason for the most common misconceptions about homosexuality is that there are many type of homosexuality and "people talking about different types as if they were one" (the end note in Scott, 1957, p. 659). A good empirical example of the desirability of such distinctions was provided by one of the formerly performed surveys, carried out by Olivier and Mosher (1968), in which significant differences were found between subgroups of homosexual insertees and inserters in regard to the results achieved by them on the MMPI and the Mosher Forced-Choice Guilt Inventory. Some of the reviewed studies have shown similar examples.

Thus, as it seems, the findings of the research could be more precise and relevant, if the scope of their validity in relation to a population range will be described more accurately.

NOTES

¹<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Adam4Adam> [last access: 21.10.2013].

²<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Manhunt.net> [last access: 21.10.2013].

³<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gay.com> [last access: 21.10.2013].

⁴<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gayromeo> [last access: 21.10.2013].

⁵[http:// http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gaydar_\(website\)](http://http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gaydar_(website)) [last access: 21.10.2013].

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